

EARTH SCIENCES

GAS POTENTIAL OF EAGLE FORD / AGUA NUEVA FORMATION IN MEXICO

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Abstract

The paper provides an assessment of the HC potential of the clay-carbonate shales of the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation within the extension on the territory of Mexico. Using the example of a small area located in the gas condensate generation and accumulation zone, the prospective of the development and production of hydrocarbons from the Eagle Ford formation, extending into Mexico as the Agua Nueva formation, are shown. The key role of the principle of cyclic development of shale deposits from the first years of production is shown, which will allow achieving high values of accumulated hydrocarbon production per well and significantly increasing economic profitability. The production of natural gas from the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation will allow Mexico to gain gas independence by 2036, with production starting in 2027.

Keywords: clay-carbonate shales, hydrocarbons (HC), HC kitchen, abnormal high reservoir pressure (AHRP), catagenesis, resource base, condensate, cyclic shale production, potential balance method, organic matter (OM), pressure of fluid fracturing (Pffr)

The United Mexican States has a high potential for increasing the production of petroleum hydrocarbons from the Pimienta shale formation (Vera Cruz State), heavy oils in Tampico province and on the southern shelf of the Gulf of Mexico in the Sur Este basin. However, industrially large accumulations of gas in traditional reservoirs in Mexico have not yet been discovered (but there are small gas discoveries offshore the state of Veracruz). Associated (dissolved) gas produced during the production of all known oil fields onshore and offshore Mexico is mainly used for the needs of the oil industry and consumed by PEMEX (about 4

BCF/day). Almost all of the gas to fully meet Mexico's needs (6-7 BCF/day) is purchased in the United States at the current price of \$3/CF (Fig. 1), while the United States sells gas for Europe at price of \$12-13/CF. And if the United States raises the gas price for Mexico, it will become a serious problem for the country's economy and, first of all, for the population. In this regard, Mexico needs to start solving the problem of gas energy independence right now, since there is no alternative to gas supplies from other countries in South and Central America.

Fig. 1. Natural gas production and consumption in Mexico, MCF/day (by EIA, CNH u CONACYT, 2024-2025).

The fastest possible solution to this problem in terms of adequate implementation is possible through the development of the Eagle Ford shale formation, extending from the United States to Mexico, where it is called Agua Nueva formation. Large oil, gas, and condensate fields have already been discovered and are actively being developed in South Texas (USA), associated with the Eagle Ford shale formation, which are being developed by El Paso, Anadarko, EOG, Chevron, Petrohawk, Pioneer, and other companies. Extensive experience has been gained in the exploration and production of HC shales in South Texas fields, from exploration, drilling, completion and production. The noted positive results of the shales development will become drivers for assessing the HC availability in the continuation of the Eagle Ford formation within the Mexico.

The Eagle Ford oil kitchen formation extends into the Mexican territory at approximately the same depths and with similar thermobaric parameters as in the United States. In order to assess the prospects for the development of the Eagle Ford /Agua Nueva shale formation in Mexico, the authors selected a pilot square area of about 1000 km² (Fig. 2) [5, 7]. The initial data for the assessment were materials from the development of adjacent

fields Red Hawk (shale oil), Blue Hawk (shale gas condensate), Hawkville (shale gas) in southern Texas, and other similar fields, as well as data (IHS, 2014) from the Eagle Ford/Agua formation drilled wells in Mexico: Chucula-1, Durian-1, Emergente-1, Montanes-1.

Fig. 2. Structural map of Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation with catagenesis zonation.

1 – isohypses, ft; 2 – pilot area; 3 – borders of catagenesis zonation; 4 – wells: a) in Mexico, b) in “oil window”, c) in “wet gas window”; 5 – shale fields in Texas; 6 – The U.S.-Mexico state border [5, 7].

Using the example of the Eagle Ford formation (USA) and other regions, based on the developed methodological approaches [5, 7] to calculating the hydrocarbon potential of shale reservoirs, the basic principles of the geological study and assessment of the oil and gas potential of the territory under consideration and the assessment of HC resources in shale deposits within the pilot area in Mexico [2-7].

From the experience of developing shale deposits, their advantages and disadvantages for the territory under consideration are determined.

Among the factors positively influencing the prospects for HC shale production in Mexico, the following can be noted: significant distribution areas, large

volumes of shale rocks with a high content of TOC; low licenses cost (at the initial stage); a large number of already discovered deposits in neighboring areas in the United States and accumulated production experience; minimal costs for the exploration of non-structural deposits; the available information on the fulfilled geological exploration activities, proximity to sales markets in a region with a relatively developed infrastructure.

Among the disadvantages negatively affecting the prospects for production it can be noted: the lack of Mexico's own experience in the development of HC shale deposits; geological risks, high production costs at the initial stage of development; rapid depletion of

deposits (productivity of existing wells decreases much faster than in traditional fields): the current state restrictions on the implementation of hydraulic fracturing for the shale formations development.

Stratigraphy, lithology, and tectonics. The Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation is confined to the lower part of the Upper Cretaceous at depths within the pilot area from 2,600 to 3,100 m. The sediments of the formation lie on a monocline that smoothly sinks to the center of the Mexican megasyncline and is complicated by sub latitudinal faults. Deposits are not traditional types of traps.

Source rocks. In the source rocks, the content of organic matter (sapropel type) varies in the range of 2-9%. Based on the actual values measured in the wells of fields in Texas, the average value of the TOC (4.50%) for the pilot area was assumed.

The rocks of the formation are represented by dense limestones (calcite content 45-55%), mudstones and quartz and can be characterized as HC clay-carbonate shales, which are a transitional rock complex from the underlying carbonate deposits to the overlying clays.

The high content of calcite and organics is explained by the rocks accumulation in the conditions of the shelf margin and the continental slope. The rock density is 2.7 t/m³ for calcite, the densest mineral of the Eagle Ford formation. The sedimentation interbedded of rocks is largely due to the deposition of fossilized organic matter on the stratification planes, which creates characteristic mesostructures, as well as its uneven concentration at various stages of sediment accumulation. The rock layers are identical in structural and textural features and have the same mineral composition, which indicates minor changes in the hydrodynamic environment of their deposition [7].

Therobaric conditions of source rocks. Oil and gas bearing rocks are characterized by abnormally high temperature and reservoir pressure relative to background values. At the area under consideration and at similar deposits, an abnormally high temperature (usually due to a high focal magma level) heats up the clay-carbonate sediments, regardless of their depth and initial catagenesis, and initiates active processes of lithogenetic changes of the organic-mineral substances and the release of catagenesis products. It is also known that in the process of fracturing, as a result of fluid fracturing and the resulting phenomenon of cavitation, a pulse of high local temperature (> 300°C) occurs. The process of redistribution of heat resulting from this impact mechanism, directed towards thermal equilibrium in the system, eventually forms a geothermal anomaly in HC saturated rocks [1, 3].

Reservoir temperatures have abnormally high values in productive zones, both in the United States and in Mexico, where they vary depending on the depth of occurrence from 90 to 170 °C, and within the pilot area from 130 to 147°C (Fig. 2). Abnormally high reservoir pressure (AHRP) of the formation is also caused by the thermal expansion of the formed hydrocarbons in the process of their destruction (catagenesis) in an enclosed space. Enriched carbon layers inside a thick layer of almost impermeable rocks ensure reliable hydrodynamic

insulation of hydrocarbons. The pressure values measured at the Eagle Ford formation in the US fields and extrapolated to the Mexico vary from 30 to 70 MPa (47-58 MPa in the pilot area) while hydrostatic are 20-45 MPa, which corresponds to the AHRP (anomaly is of about 1.9) characteristic of HC shale formations (Fig. 3).

HC generation potential and oil and gas zonation. Depending on the thermobaric conditions and the gradation of OM catagenesis, the source rocks generate hydrocarbons of a certain composition and phase state. Previously, a catagenetic anomaly (forced catagenesis of OM and rocks) was established in the oil-saturated Khadum and Batalpashinsky clay shales (Central and Eastern Ciscaucasia) [1, 3, 5]. At Texan fields, vertical zonation of oil and gas formation conditions has been established in a relatively narrow depth range (1200-5200 m), where all three main phases of oil, gas condensate and dry gas formation are concentrated. This zonation, which is not disturbed by migration processes, indicates the presence of a catagenetic anomaly and allows for a highly reliable directional exploration for HC deposits of a certain phase state in a narrow area and certain deep range (Fig. 4) [2, 4, 5, 7].

In accordance with this zonation, oil deposits (oil window) are generated and formed in-situ where the OM of clay-carbonate rocks has reached MK₃¹-MK₄¹ grades of catagenesis. Where the OM of rocks has reached MK₃¹-MK₄¹ grades, gas condensate deposits are formed (wet gas window), and where OM has reached the MK₄²-AK₁² degree, hydrocarbon gases are formed (dry gas window), where, as is known, gas generation occurs regardless of the OM type [2, 4, 5]. Taking into account the opinions of various authors [5, 6], the amount of HC generation containing dispersed OM ranges from 2 to 6 m³/t at TOC = 1% for gas at depths of 3-4 km. The zones of wet and dry gas differ of the condensate content: from zero in the dry gas zone to 1180 g/m³ (Black Hawk).

Data on the vitrinite reflectivity and the actual productivity of shale formations based on the results of production wells drilling in the Texas (USA) allow us to confidently build an oil and gas zonation (Fig. 1) of the entire territory under consideration (including adjacent areas of Mexico) [2-7].

The pilot area in the Mexico is located in the zone of the gas condensate window (Fig. 1). The total thickness of Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation is on average almost twice as large as in the adjacent fields in south Texas (Fig. 5), which may indicate a significantly larger the generation potential of the formation in Mexico comparing with the neighboring territory of south Texas. Significantly thicker formation reduce the risks of water breakout from the overlying (Austin Chalk / San Felipe) and underlying Buda formation during the hydraulic fracturing and further production.

Reservoir properties of shale reservoirs are formed due to highly permeable natural and secondary (because of hydraulic fracturing) fractures. Unlike clay shale formations, clay-carbonate shales have a more compact structure of the pore space. A small pore volume causes a small HC fraction per unit of deposit volume. Fractures with a small volume work just with

AHRP presence. At the same time, if for dry gas (even with very low permeability) the pore size is still comparable to the size of a gas molecule (with a small condensate content), then for oil the permeability should be much higher. Hence, the productivity of dense clay-carbonate shales is associated with fractures, the volume of HC reserves of which in the total mass of the rock is

no more than 5-10% due to the low porosity of 1-1.5%. Therefore, when talking about a porosity of 3-7% of dense rocks, this does not mean that the pores contain fluid (just minor inflows), since clay-carbonate interbedded sediments have high fracturing, which is the main reservoir [1-6].

Fig. 3. Isotherm map Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation (agenda on fig. 1) [5]

Fig. 4. Isobar map Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation (agenda on fig. 1) [5, 7]

Fig. 5. Map of the total thickness of the Eagle Ford/ Agua Nueva formation, ft (agenda on fig. 1) [5, 7]

The mechanism of formation of a fractured reservoir is considered in detail in the books [5, 6]. The formation of fractures occurs in an isolated system due to the thermal expansion of liquid and gaseous catagenesis products. The behavior of the fluids is controlled by the critical values of the created pressure (Pcr), which is equal to the pressure of fluid fracturing (Pffr). The reservoir capacity increases due to the appearance of new and existing fractures, where HC accumulations increase. Thus, the horizontal fracturing of the rocks ensures the shale reservoir properties.

Genesis of deposits. Oil and gas clay-carbonate shales are both an oil source stratum, a reservoir and a fluid barrier rocks. At the same time, the processes of formation of reservoir capacity in clay-carbonate rocks, PC deposits and abnormal high reservoir pressure are intertwined in time, space and are interdependent. Researchers disagree on the question of the HC genesis in shales. The appearance of fractures and HC accumulations are associated by most researchers with the noted phenomenon of fluid fracturing of interbedded rocks (S.G. Neruchev et al., 1987; F.Ya. Borkun, 1986; F.G. Gurari et al., 1974; A.V. Bochkarev, V.N. Evik, 1987, 1990; A.V. Bochkarev, V.I. Petrenko, 1987; M.F.Svintsov, 1973). At the same time, everyone agrees that hydrocarbons formed in shales form deposits in-situ in quasi-closed thermodynamic systems, where a HC deposit evolves in the dead ends of fluid fracturing zones. The continuously intermittent nature of the fluid fracturing process in HC-rich rocks leads to the oil, gas, and condensate accumulations of a complex non-anticlinal (catalytic) type in an isolated reservoir [5, 6].

Thus oil and gas potential of the Eagle Ford formation is associated not with the processes of long-

range or near-range HC migration, but with in-situ syngenetic HC accumulation in fractured reservoirs.

The pilot area is entirely located in the wet gas formation zone. If the license is consistently expanded to the north, the oil will account for an increasing share ("oil window"). And vice versa If expand the license in a southerly direction, it the dry gas will account for an increasing share ("dry gas window").

Condensate content (CC). The condensate content for the pilot area was assumed, according to the map of CC values, at the level of 320 g/m³ (in average) by a significant sample of actual data in the United States (Fig. 6). The average CC value for only two wells in the Mexico (wells Montanes-1 and Shukla-1), equal to 261 g/m³, may be underestimated.

The condensate content throughout the wet gas zone does not differ in the United States and Mexico (Fig. 6) and depends just on the wells location in the wet gas zone. The CC data in the Mexico, as well as in South Texas, confirm the zonality of oil and gas formation in clay-carbonate shales of Eagle Ford formation. Thus, in the Montanes-1 well, drilled at the northern boundary of the "wet gas window" on the border with the "oil window", CC has a maximum value (466 g/m³), and in the Chuclan-1 well, drilled at the boundary of the "wet gas and dry gas windows" CC by an order of magnitude less (56 g/m³). The Durian-1 and Emergente-1 wells drilled next to Chuclan-1 well but in the "dry gas zone" on Mexican territory do not contain condensate.

Assessment of HC resources. So far, there are fundamental problems in the method of HC shale resources evaluation [5, 6, 10]. Shale oil, condensate and dry gas HCIIP evaluation is possible using the volumetric genetic method of Uspensky V.A., Kozlov V.P., Tokarev L.V., Bochkarev V.A., which is based on taking into

account the total thicknesses of the oil and gas shales, the initial TOC and the source rock HC yield (HC-yield) depending on the catagenesis grade (temperature).

Taking into account the area of the pilot area (S); the total thickness of Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation (H); the amount of HC-yield, the potential TOC; rock density (ρ_{rock}) and condensate content (CC) IIP evaluation of gas (Q_{gas}) and condensate (Q_{con}) of the license area under consideration It is made according to the formula:

$$Q_{\text{gas}} = S * H * \rho_{\text{rock}} * \text{TOC} * \text{HC_yield} \quad [5, 6].$$

$$Q_{\text{con}} = Q_{\text{gas}} * \text{CC}$$

The Initial Recoverable gas and condensate reserves calculated for the pilot area (based on recoverable factor reached in USA) are comparable and even exceed similar areas in the United States.

Shale formations Explorations. The area configuration of deposits with any structural appearance of the surface of the productive stratum will resemble "ink spots", the tracing of which by seismic methods is an intractable problem. Delineation of such HC shale deposits is carried out by exploration and production wells drilling and by 3D high-resolution seismic methods (Acoustic Impedance, Diffraction energy attribute, coherence etc.). In fact, the exploration of the shale deposits is carried out according to the method "from the known to the unknown" [5].

Shale Development. The areas of greatest interest in the wet gas window area will be those where the CC exceeds 50 g/m³. Further development of such areas will not depend on the current gas price, as it will be based on the liquid hydrocarbons production, while the gas is a strategic product for Mexico.

Shale Cyclic development. The technology of long-term shale production does not require special costs (Fig. 8) [5-9].

The existing experience of the oil fields development of the Maikop clay shales (Batalpashinskaya and

Khadam formations) of the Central and Eastern Caucasus shows that after pressure drops and flow rates decrease to a minimum, wells must be preserved for a period (1-9 months) sufficient to restore reservoir pressure (well Vorobyovskaya-5) [5, 6].

Fig. 7. The scheme of the Agua Nueva formation development for the pilot area in Mexico [5, 7]

After wells are stopped to restore and compensate for reservoir pressure in a self-regulating reservoir due to the processes of continuous active HC generation, oil production rates are restored after the well stop period (sometimes close to the initial ones).

Such dynamics of oil production is confirmed by the long-term (over 30 years) development of a number

of vertical (!) wells from the Eagle Ford shale formation (Texas) (Fig. 9) [5-8]. At the same time, new wells with a horizontal completion (1000-2500 m) maximize the drainage area, higher initial flow rates and a higher accumulated production per well (10-15 times higher than at the vertical well).

Fig 8. A graph of the cyclic shale development (V.A. Bochkarev [1, 4, 5, 8])

Fig 9. A graph describing the results obtained by EOG. Recovery of well flow rates during periodic development and fracking (Malanichev A.G., 2018) [5, 7].

In similar fields of Western Siberia (HC shale of the Bazhenov formation), after a fast drop of the HC production rate, wells are temporarily preserved [13]

And the more significant production rate drop, the more significant the processes of additional HC generation, the thermal expansion of which dampens the process of reducing reservoir pressure and oil flow rate. During the wells downtime, reservoir pressure is restored in a self-regulating reservoir due to the processes of continuous active HC generation. Thus, the cyclical dynamics of changes of reservoir pressure and the intensity of oil and gas generation processes are observed. The appearance of additional HC resources is spent on the growth of AHRP and the expansion of the deposit fractured system [3, 5, 6, 7].

The estimation of the optimal number of cycles for reservoir pressure recovery and HC reserve replenishment is based on the evaluation of the shale formations generation potential and the subsequent calculation of production by the decline curves. It is recommended to stop the wells for "refueling" due to the resumption of HC generation processes from several weeks to 2-3 months (Fig. 8), depending on the initial shale formation potential (the higher the TOC and the AHRP value, the shorter the time required to generate a new HC portions).

Thus, the full life of the shale well taking into account the periodic restoration of reservoir pressure can be represented as an equation:

$$Twfl = (36+3)*N, (1)$$

where $Twfl$ is a full life of the shale well 36 are the months of operation and 3 are the months of the wells shutdowns, N is the number of cycles of HC deposits replenishment depending on the TOC and S_2 values (calculated by the Potential balance method) [5, 6, 7].

The time for shutting down wells for shale deposits may vary. The proposed cyclic shale development method has proven its validity and relevance in the Eagle Ford shale formation (USA), where it takes 1-3 months to restore the initial oil flow rate of 250-300 bpd.

Prolonged and intense disturbance of the reservoir system disrupts the natural balance, which leads to a rapid drop of reservoir pressure and a rapid decrease of flow rate. N.P. Zapivalov and I.P. Popov [11] noted that the threshold disturbance to the system can be estimated through reservoir depression, which, as detected for many HC fields should not exceed 5 MPa.

Compliance with the critical depression threshold (about 5 MPa), rehabilitation periods ("refueling") and gentle methods of increasing oil recovery are necessary conditions for long-term and effective development of oil and gas shale deposits due to the independent restoration of the natural system.

From the very beginning of the shale field development, it is necessary to ensure periodic geo-fluid dynamic monitoring and temporary production shut-downs in order to ensure the restoration of HC reserves by resuming the HC generation process. Each new development cycle should begin with repeated fracking to open remote fractures (Fig. 10).

The proposed principle of cyclic shale development will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, extend the life (operation) of existing wells and reduce the CAPEX in general. This approach allows to preserve the generation potential of the developed formations, provides the compliance with the critical depression threshold (about 5 MPa), the implementation of rehabilitation periods ("refueling" for 0.5-2.5 months) and gentle methods of increasing oil and gas recovery due to the independent restoration of the natural system.

The use of cyclic HC shale development of the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva shale formation in Mexico will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of operational wells, prolong the life (operation) of already drilled wells and reduce the CAPEX in general [5-9].

Economy. The cost of production of shale oil, natural gas, and condensate has now approached the level of fields with traditional reservoirs (Fig. 7) [12], outstripping heavy oil fields and deepwater projects. The

upper level of profitability of gas prices for the US market in 2025 is around \$2/1000CF (~\$70/1000m3).

The use of cyclic development of the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation with the repeated hydraulic fracturing in existing wells will allow achieving greater accumulated production per well than for wells in the United States and thereby reduce drilling of additional wells, significantly improving the economic performance of HC shale development in Mexico.

The continuation of the Eagle Ford formation to Mexico occurs for the areas of the generation and accumulation of oil, condensate and dry gas. The economic

efficiency of dry gas development of the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation will be enhanced, among other things, by oil and condensate production. At the same time, natural gas has a high index of NGL (Natural Gas Liquids) and thus can bring additional profit.

The development of the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva shale formation in Mexico starting with 2026 will allow producing by 2030 an additional 3 BCF/day (Fig. 11) of the natural

Fig 10. The principle scheme of cyclic shale development.

gas, and by 2036 to reach the production level of about 8 BCF/day, which will fully cover the daily consumption of natural gas for the country, subject to optimization of the useful use of gas by the state-owned company PEMEX (starting from 2027-2028), which in combination with the production of traditional gas

(mainly associated gas) will ensure the energy independence of Mexico in the future until 2050-2060 years (taking into account the implementation of cyclical shale development) at current gas consumption levels of the country.

Fig. 11. The forecast of natural gas production in Mexico until 2050 due to the development of shale gas formations (primarily Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva in the state of Coahuila), since 2027 (according to the EIA, CNH and CONACYT, 2024-2025 and the authors' forecast).

Summary:

The Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation extension to the territory of Mexico has a high potential for the development of shale gas and condensate.

The HCIP of the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation in Mexico may amount to hundreds of billions CF of gas and tens of millions barrels of liquid hydrocarbons.

The start of development of the Eagle Ford shale formation in Mexico since 2026 will fully allow for an additional 3 BCF/day of gas to be produced by 2030, and by 2036 to ensure Mexico's long-term gas independent.

To achieve gas production from the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva shale formation, it will require drilling about 1,600 horizontal wells a year (taking into account the cyclic development approach) since 2029, with a horizontal completion of 1,500-2,000 m and a number of 15-20 fracturing sections (every 100 m).

The principle of cyclic development of HC shale will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of operational wells, prolong the life (operation) of existing wells, achieve high values of accumulated HC production per well and significantly increase the economic performance of development (IRR>20).

The development and production of the HC shale of the Eagle Ford/Agua Nueva formation will provide thousands of jobs and enable the implementation of many social projects in the states of Coahuila and Nuevo Leon in Mexico. The Piedras Negras city may become a major industrial center of HC shale production.

Since 2037, Mexico will be able to export some of its natural gas to closest neighbors in Central America (Guatemala, Honduras, El Salvador).

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